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**The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and
Learning Citizen Science in Europe**

D2.1: Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report

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Definitions and Acronyms

CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
DG-Env	European Commission Directorate-General for Environment
EC	European Commission
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association /Verein der Europäischen Bürgerwissenschaften
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020
LULC	land-use and land-cover change
PPSR	Public Participation in Scientific Research
the Platform	The EU-Citizen.Science platform
the Project	The EU-Citizen.Science project
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
Stakeholders	Those who have a stake or interest in the success of the Platform and the outcomes of the Project
Target Audience	Those groups who we wish to actively seek out to use the Platform, and engage with in the community of Users
Users	Those who will use the Platform
QH	The Quadruple Helix model

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Executive Summary

The *'EU-Citizen.Science Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report'* is Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1) within the Coordination and Support Action (CSA) EU-Citizen.Science. The ambition of EU-Citizen.Science is to build, fill, and promote a sustainable platform and mutual learning space providing different tools, best practice examples and relevant scientific outcomes that are collected, curated, and made accessible to different stakeholders, ranging from interested citizens over scientific institutions up to politicians and public media in order to mainstream citizen science in Europe.

This deliverable maps and describes the key actors and interested parties whose support and involvement will ensure the success of the EU-Citizen.Science platform. This is accomplished by systematically reviewing the individuals and organisations who play a key role in citizen science activities in general, who are likely to also become the core users of the EU-Citizen.Science platform in particular.

The main objectives of this report are to:

- Deepen our understanding of the full range of stakeholders in citizen science,
- Identify the key stakeholders for the success of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, as users, contributors, and/or supporters,
- Expand our working definition of the relevant stakeholder categories and the relationship they are likely to have to the Platform
- Form the foundation for other core tasks and activities within the EU-Citizen.Science project across a range of Work Packages.

The primary stakeholder groups that we hereby identify, analyse, map and prioritise are: Academia, The Public, NGOs & CSOs, Industry & SMEs, The Press & Media, Policy Makers & Funders, and Educators.

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1 Introduction

1.1 The EU-Citizen.Science Project

Citizen science (CS) actively involves the public in scientific research that generates new knowledge or understanding, and thus has the potential to bring together science, society and policy makers in an impactful way. As a core dimension of Open Science, it opens up the opportunity for all members of society to take an active role in research, innovation and the development of evidence-based policy, at local, national and EU levels.

It is the ambition of the EU-Citizen.Science project (‘the Project’) to build on the growing impact of citizens participating in research across the full range of scientific enquiry, by developing a sustainable platform to act as a mutual learning space for citizen science, focusing on Europe, but relevant globally. The overall vision for the EU-Citizen.Science platform (‘the Platform’) is to aid the mainstreaming of citizen science in Europe, such that it becomes an appreciated and widely established means for the democratisation of science in Europe, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: The Vision, Mission and Objectives of the EU-Citizen.Science project

The building of the Platform is being pursued through three interconnected lines of activity:

1. Coordinating citizen science actions, and making use of existing resources in the presently fragmented citizen science landscape in Europe,
2. Engaging quadruple helix stakeholders at local, national and European levels, and
3. Creating a mutual learning space and a set of comprehensive, co-designed training modules for different target audiences.

In keeping with our mission, we aim to engage equally with citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society throughout the course of the project. In order to do so effectively, it is therefore necessary to have a clear view of our stakeholders - both in the success of the project, and the usefulness of the platform itself.

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1.2 The Purpose of this Deliverable

The second work package within the Project (*WP2: Platform, Community and Network Building*) forms both the foundation and the heart of the Project, and is where the core work of co-designing and implementing the Platform is performed.

WP2 contains three crucial assessment phases - the first of which is to identify the key stakeholders of the EU.Citizen.Science platform and its stated objectives. This work takes place within Task 2.1 *'Mapping of stakeholders, key networks & platform-community members; multi-level engagement model for community and network building'*, culminating in two deliverables: Deliverable 2.1 *'Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report'*, which is this report, and Deliverable 2.2 *'Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan'*, which will be submitted in parallel to this report.

The purpose of this D2.1 stakeholder report is to map the key actors and interested parties whose support and involvement will ensure the success of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, in order to:

- Deepen our understanding of the full range of stakeholders in citizen science,
- Identify the key stakeholders for the success of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, as users, contributors, and/or supporters,
- Expand our working definition of the relevant stakeholder categories and the relationship they are likely to have to the Platform
- Form the foundation for other core tasks and activities within the EU-Citizen.Science project across a range of work packages.

Involving both active and potential stakeholders throughout the planning and development of the platform will be crucial to ensuring its success. This report also forms the basis for the subsequent requirements-gathering activities that are contained within Task 2.2 *'Co-design of platform requirements (including end-user / community needs assessment and analysis of content formats'*, which will culminate in Deliverable 2.3 *'Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report'*.

There is a strong interlinkage between these three WP2 deliverables, as the aim of D2.3 is to ensure that the interests and needs of the stakeholders identified are represented in the building of the platform, in order to ensure its usefulness, impact, and ultimate success.

1.3 The Scope of this Deliverable

This Deliverable undertakes a review of the full heterogeneous range of individuals and organisations who have a stake in the success of the Project and the Platform - from active CS practitioner or user of CS outcomes, to those who are new to CS - and presents a stakeholder map of the key actors and interested parties. This report does *not* attempt a comprehensive review of all actors involved in individual citizen science projects, as they are highly specific to the stated goals of each project, the domain of enquiry, and the location of the project.

This report also does not attempt to identify policy or other local stakeholders at a more granular level, as this work will be performed in Work Package 4 *'Awareness and Engagement - Public and Policy Makers'* within Task 4.1 *'Achieving societal awareness and engagement in science through existing citizen-science networks, projects and multiplier event'*, where task leader Earthwatch will assist partners in identifying stakeholders, audiences and activities at the local level.

As noted above, WP2 contains three crucial assessment phases - the first of which is the focus of this report. The identification of the needs and requirements of all stakeholders is a consolidated cross-consortium activity that then feeds into the subsequent work packages, and will form the

basis for Deliverable 2.2 ‘Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan’, submitted in parallel to this report, and Deliverable 2.3 ‘Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report’ to be submitted in month 12 of the Project.

2 Methodology

2.1 Stakeholder Mapping & Analysis

Stakeholder Mapping & Analysis is the systematic process of determining the individuals, organisations and groups that have an interest in a project or initiative, and are impacted by its outcomes. It is ideally a collaborative process that draws on research, input from multiple perspectives and discussion to create a list of key stakeholders across as wide a spectrum as possible. The stakeholder mapping and analysis process can typically be broken down into four phases:

1. **Identifying:** listing relevant groups, organizations, and people
2. **Analyzing:** understanding stakeholder perspectives and interests,
3. **Mapping:** visualizing relationships to objectives and other stakeholders, and
4. **Prioritizing:** ranking stakeholder relevance and identifying issues.¹

Stakeholder approaches and concepts within the business and management literature date back as far as the early 1930s, and encompass a wide range of different methodologies. However, stakeholder analysis typically focuses on two key elements: 1) the interest that stakeholders take in a particular issue and, 2) the quantity and types of resources they can mobilize to affect outcomes (Crosby, 1992;² Brinkerhoff, 1991³). Such analyses can be summarised in an Influence/Interest Matrix (See Figure 2 below) that is easy to read and useful for strategic communications planning.

Figure 2: Stakeholder Map showing interest and influence.

¹ Step 2, of the BSR Five-Step Approach to Stakeholder Engagement. <https://www.bsr.org/en/>

² Crosby B. 1992. Stakeholder analysis: a vital tool for strategic managers. Washington DC: USAID

³ Brinkerhoff, Derick W., Improving Development Program Performance. Boulder, Colorado: Lynne Rienner Publishers, 1991

When identifying parties that are or will be affected by, and thus “have a stake in” a course of action or particular issue, it is important to also prioritize them according to their level of interest in and influence over the project, and seek to understand more about them in order to engage and communicate with them effectively.

The Stakeholder Register lists the stakeholder groups according to these prioritisations, and indicates which groups should be included in which communications, consultations and co-design activities. Walton et al, 2013⁴ describe a series of five progressive stages (shown in Figure 3 below) throughout a project in which stakeholders may participate, engage or otherwise have a stake, which provides further detail for engagement across the project lifecycle:

Figure 3: Steps of Traditional Stakeholder Participatory Processes (Walton et al. 2013)

2.2 Stakeholder Mapping in Citizen Science

Skarlatidou et al, 2019 identify three different types of stakeholder maps: (1) descriptive (those that describe how stakeholders behave and their actions), (2) normative (those that focus on “the legitimacy of stakeholder involvement and empowerment in decision making processes”) and (3) instrumental (those that focus on how CS projects “can identify, explain, and manage the behaviour of stakeholders to achieve desired outcomes”; Reed, et al., 2009, pp. 1935-1936).⁵

The three methodologies that they deployed for their in-depth stakeholder mapping investigation within the DITOs project are particularly well-suited for use in co-created citizen science initiatives that require good engagement with all who are involved.

At its core, citizen science revolves around partnerships between professional scientists and the public (citizen scientists) in conducting scientific research together (Miller-Rushing et al., 2012).⁶ A wide range of stakeholders are thus frequently involved within any given citizen science project:

⁴ Walton A. Gomei M. and Di Carlo G. 2013. STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT. Participatory Approaches for the Planning and Development of Marine Protected Areas. World Wide Fund for Nature and NOAA—National Marine Sanctuary Program

⁵ Skarlatidou, A., Suskevics, M., Göbel, C., Prüse, B., Tauginienė, L., Mascarenhas, A., Mazzonetto, M., Sheppard, A., Barrett, J., Haklay, M., Baruch, A., Moraitopoulou, E-A., Austen, K., Baž, I., Berditchevskaja, A., Berényi, E., Hoyte, S., Kleijssen, L., Kragh, G., Legris, M., Mansilla-Sanchez, A., Nold, C., Vitos, M., Wyszomirski, P. (2019). The value of stakeholder mapping to enhance co-creation in citizen science initiatives. Citizen Science: Theory and Practice (in-print)

⁶ Miller-Rushing, A., Primack, R. and Bonney, R. 2012. The history of public participation in ecological research. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*, 10: 285–290. DOI:10.1890/110278.

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“Given its collaborative nature, citizen science is characterized by a wide range of stakeholders, whose motivations and interactions can be determinant for the success of a citizen science project and thus should be carefully taken into account on project design.”⁷

One key to understanding the complexities that a wide range of actors bring is to go beyond simply identifying the relevant stakeholders involved and the possibilities for their involvement, to also identifying their interaction dynamics (Skarlatidou et al, 2019).⁸

“We argue that a better understanding of stakeholder involvement may contribute to more effective stakeholder communication, more successful implementation and a greater impact for citizen science initiatives.”⁹

This approach to stakeholder mapping has several benefits, as identified by Skarlatidou et al, 2019 in their review of the literature¹⁰:

1. Including all relevant stakeholder groups means that projects are designed to have wider impacts (Wiggins and Crowston, 2011)¹¹; identifying potential stakeholders early can result in effective mechanisms to support their timely involvement.
2. Sharing data and information in citizen science requires an in-depth understanding of stakeholders across many levels (Göbel et al., 2017;¹² Mazumdar et al., 2017;¹³ Newman et al., 2012¹⁴).
3. Communication mechanisms between stakeholders can be effective if there is a good understanding of those involved (Roy et al., 2012)¹⁵.
4. It can provide the first step to engaging new audiences (Pandya, et al., 2012)¹⁶, including ‘harder to reach’ stakeholders.

⁷ Tiago, P., 2016. Social Context of Citizen Science Projects. In: Ceccaroni, L. and Jaume, P.(eds.) Analyzing the Role of Citizen Science in Modern Research. Hershey, PA: IGI Global. pp. 168–191. DOI: 10.4018/978-1-5225-0962-2.ch008.

⁸ Skarlatidou et al, 2019.

⁹ Skarlatidou et al, 2019.

¹⁰ Skarlatidou et al, 2019

¹¹ Wiggins, A. and Crowston, K., 2011. From Conservation to Crowdsourcing: A Typology of Citizen Science. In:44th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, Kauai, USA, 4–7 January 2011, pp. 1-10. DOI: 10.1109/HICSS.2011.207.

¹² Göbel, C., Martin, V.Y. and Ramirez-Andreotta, M., 2017. Stakeholder Analysis: International Citizen Science Stakeholder Analysis on Data Interoperability. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson International Centre for Scholars. Available at <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/international-citizen-science-stakeholder-analysis>

¹³ Mazumdar, S., Wrigley, S. and Ciravegna, F., 2017. Citizen Science and Crowdsourcing for Earth Observations: An Analysis of Stakeholder Opinions on the Present and Future. Remote Sensing, 9(1): 87. DOI: 10.3390/rs9010087.

¹⁴ Newman, G., Wiggins, A., Crall, A., Graham, E., Newman, S. and Crowston, K., 2012. The future of citizen science: emerging technologies and shifting paradigms. Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment, 10(6): 298–304. DOI: 10.1890/110294

¹⁵ Roy, H.E., Pocock, M.J.O., Preston, C.D., Roy, D.B., Savage, J., Tweddle, J.C., and Robinson, L.D., 2012. Understanding Citizen Science and Environmental Monitoring: Final report on behalf of UK Environmental Observation Framework. NERC Centre for Ecology & Hydrology and Natural History Museum. Available at <https://www.ceh.ac.uk/sites/default/files/citizensciencereview.pdf>

¹⁶ Pandya, R.E., 2012. A framework for engaging diverse communities in citizen science in the US. Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment, 10: 314–317. DOI: 10.1890/120007.

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5. Projects can benefit from harnessing the complex and comprehensive local (or, in other contexts, indigenous) knowledge these groups possess.

2.3 The Stakeholders in EU-Citizen.Science

In defining the scope of this report, we must first highlight that our focus is those who are Stakeholders in the success of the Project, and in the success of the Platform. There is a highly specific range of potential stakeholders within any given citizen science project, depending on the domain of research and the stated aims of the project, and we do not cover them here.

We thus define our stakeholders as ‘Any person, group, or entity with a common interest or stake in the outcomes of the Project and the success of the Platform’, as shown in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Our approach to stakeholder identification and assessment

STAKEHOLDER	Any person, group, or entity with a common interest or stake in the outcomes of the project and the success of the platform
ROLE	Each stakeholder may assume one or more roles, and may be a user of the platform as well as a stakeholder.
INTEREST	How will the project impact the stakeholder? How will the stakeholder benefit from the outcomes of the project?
THEIR NEEDS	What are the primary concerns of this stakeholder? What expectations do they have? What will influence their support?
OUR NEEDS	What do we need from this stakeholder? Resources? Approval? Visible public support? Access? Input?
PLANNING	How should we work with this stakeholder? How will we communicate, and how frequently? How will we address their concerns?

From the very start of the proposal-writing stage, the Project has engaged with key actors who are implementing citizen science initiatives at the European level (either as project coordinators, project partners, third parties or project supporters), together with newcomers who can introduce and promote citizen science practices in their respective countries. The outcomes of our first such stakeholder mapping session are contained in [Section 3](#) below, and resulted in a clear picture of the main stakeholder groupings for the Project, as shown in Figure 4 below.

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Figure 4: The main Stakeholder groupings in EU-Citizen.Science

The Consortium itself, which consists of 14 partners and 9 third parties from 14 European Member States, also reflects a wide variety of stakeholder groups ranging from universities, NGOs, local authorities, CSOs, SMEs and natural history museums.

2.4 Stakeholders vs Users vs Target Audience

Having thus defined ‘stakeholders’ for the purpose of this report, it is important to note that there is a great deal of overlap between actors who have a stake in the success and impact of the Platform (the Stakeholders), those who will use the Platform (‘the Users’), and those groups who we wish to actively seek out and engage with, including those who are not yet involved in CS in any way and might not even be familiar with the term (‘the Target Audience’).

More attention will be paid to the description of our Users and our Target Audience in the D2.2 *‘Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan’* and in the D2.3 *‘Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report’* - as the Platform that we are building, and the community that we are building around that, must meet the needs and requirements of both groups in order to be successful.

The core User groupings for the Platform can be divided into those who are ‘producers’ of Citizen Science, i.e. people who do Citizen Science, and those who are ‘consumers’ of Citizen Science, i.e. those who use the outcomes of Citizen Science. Both groups contain people who are acting in different contexts, as shown in Figure 5 below, and also reflect a range of experience levels from those who are new to CS (‘Interested’) to those who have active experience with CS (‘Active’).

Figure 5: The two core user groups of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform

As people within these user groups start to make use of the Platform and engage with the community, their stake in how well the Platform performs its functions will increase, and so they should be considered as entering the map of stakeholders over the course of the Project.

Additionally, it is the stated aim of the Project to ‘Advance citizen science into the mainstream of public engagement, science communication and education’ by actively promoting and raising awareness about citizen science amongst groups who are not traditionally reached, or not yet engaged with CS. These people are very much at the core of our Target Audience for the Platform, but may not find their way naturally there as Practitioners or ‘Consumers’ of CS without our intervention.

These Target Audience groupings will thus also become Users over time, if we are successful in our communication and engagement aims, and will thus become Stakeholders as well over time.

2.5 Our Methodology and Approach

In order to compile a Stakeholder Map and Analysis for the EU-Citizen.Science project, we have followed the classic four-step approach referred to above, i.e. 1) Identifying, 2) Analyzing, 3) Mapping, and 4) Prioritizing.

In order to be as collaborative as possible, we have combined several approaches within this task: a) a review of the literature; b) a review of existing guidelines and best practices for stakeholder mapping; c) collaborative workshops with key stakeholders; and d) interviews with EU-Citizen.Science partners.

In the first section of this report, we present the outcomes of the initial stakeholder identification exercise that took place during preparation of the project proposal, which forms the basis from which the stakeholder mapping activities described in T2.1 ‘*Mapping of stakeholders, key networks & platform-community members; multi-level engagement model for community and network building*’ take place.

We then conduct a review of the literature for best practice in the identification and mapping of project stakeholders, descriptions and analyses of stakeholder groups in citizen science, and typologies by which to map these groups, thus providing us with the structure for our Stakeholder Analysis Matrix in [Section 7](#) below. Field-specific stakeholder assessments of currently active citizen science and citizen observatory projects have also served as valuable ‘sense-check’ sources.

In our survey of practitioners in the field we have pursued a purposive sampling strategy rather than a wide consultation process, in order to maximise the gathering of knowledge and expertise

of fellow practitioners in a timely manner, to feed into key Project tasks at the outset of the Project.

The outcomes of the stakeholder analysis exercise are contained in the Stakeholder Register, which is an online living document, a snapshot of which is shared in [Appendices 1, 2 and 3](#) below.

3 Literature Review: Stakeholder Typologies

As described in [Section 2](#) above, we have conducted a focused review of the literature, building on existing results and experiences, in order to highlight the research papers and guideline documents that are the most informative for our own stakeholder mapping exercise. These are summarised below.

3.1 The Quadruple Helix Model

The Quadruple Helix Model (as illustrated in Figure 6 below) promotes a collaborative multidisciplinary approach between government, industry, academia and civil society in order to create new shared value for all participants within an open innovation ecosystem¹⁷:

“Both the Triple Helix (TH) concept and the Quadruple Helix (QH) approach are grounded on the idea that innovation is the outcome of an interactive process involving different spheres of actors, each contributing according to its ‘institutional’ function in society... Contribution to innovation is envisaged in terms of sharing of knowledge and transfer of know-how, with the helices models assigning and formalising a precise role to each sphere in supporting economic growth through innovation.¹⁸”

Figure 6: The Quadruple Helix model (Van Waart et al., 2015a)¹⁹

¹⁷ <https://blog.innocentive.com/quadruple-helix-model-of-open-innovation>

¹⁸ Cavallini, Simona, et al. "Using the quadruple helix approach to accelerate the transfer of research and innovation results to regional growth." Consortium Progress Consulting Srl & Fondazione FoRmit (2016). Pg. 5

¹⁹ Harbers, Maaiké & Van Waart, Peter & Visser, Eva. (2015). Value Sensitive Design of Smart Cities.

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The QH model is prevalent throughout the Horizon 2020 Programme, as an important feature of research tackling a wide range of societal questions, and is especially relevant for citizen science approaches due to the central role that members of civil society play. In their review of how the fourth helix (Civil Society) is defined in the literature, Cavallini et al (2016) found that:

“Most of the proposed QH approaches focus on innovation generated by citizens. Social inclusion, user-centrality, and creativity have been encompassed in the knowledge production process as essential elements and civil society has been added as a fourth helix of the innovation system.”²⁰

This model thus provides an important structural foundation to our analysis, as we expand the four helices to encompass the 6 distinct actor groups described in [Figure 7](#) below. (ie. Academia, the Public, Industry, The Press, Policy Makers, and Educators) We use our expanded model to provide structure to a range of typologies, explored below, with which we can more clearly understand the varying stakeholder groups.

3.2 The Five Governance Models

When looking at participation in CS initiatives, the focus tends to be placed on the degree and the quality of the participation. These are both important facets for understanding and describing stakeholders, however for the desired outcomes of the project to be fully achieved, it is also important to identify the relationship between these two facets and how they therefore should be handled within the project.

In their paper on Public Participation in Scientific Research (PPSR), Shirk et al, 2012 define five distinctive governance models in order to provide a common framework for how PPSR opportunities are structured for public participation, and how project design can therefore positively influence and impact project outcomes. These differentiated governance models are described as being:

1. Contractual,
2. Contributory,
3. Collaborative,
4. Co-created and
5. Collegial²¹.

These models represent different roles and responsibilities that members of the public may play in citizen science research. This well-recognized typology enables us to explore our identification of Stakeholders of both the Project and Platform from a fresh perspective, considering the ways in which they may engage with either, and each other. For example, the consortium partners have a contractual relationship with the Project, the wider CS community will hopefully contribute existing materials to the Platform, and active working groups such as those in ECSA and the CS Cost Action may collaboratively create new materials to address gaps.

3.3 The Nature and Level of Stakeholder Involvement

Most assessments of the nature and level of stakeholder involvement that are presented in the literature, are from the perspective of engagement in the underlying research tasks and activities

²⁰ Cavallini et al, 2016. pg. 15

²¹ Shirk, Jennifer, Heidi Ballard, Candie Wilderman, Tina Phillips, Andrea Wiggins, Rebecca Jordan, Ellen McCallie et al. “Public participation in scientific research: a framework for deliberate design.” *Ecology and Society* 17, no. 2 (2012).

of a given citizen science project. For example, in the study of citizen science projects conducted by Göbel et al. (2017), civil society organizations, informal groups and community members, and academic and research organizations reported the highest level of involvement in the citizen science projects surveyed.

Also in the case of EU-Citizen.Science, different stakeholder groups are likely to exhibit greatly varying levels of involvement. High levels of involvement would thus include core roles within the Consortium, it's Third-party Partners, and the Advisory Board. High levels of involvement amongst users of the Platform would include active participation in the community forums and contributions of content. Low levels of involvement might for example be those who only follow Project developments via our "broadcast" communication channels, or receive formal progress reports from the Project.

3.4 Internal & external, actual & potential stakeholders

A further differentiation was made in the study of CS projects conducted by Göbel et al., 2017, between stakeholders who are internal or external to a given citizen science project, and those who are actual or potential.

"The distribution of internal and external stakeholders varied according to the governance model. For instance, in co-created and collegial projects, the project team was usually much larger than in other governance models, and included various stakeholders in making decisions"

Table 2: Matrix of Stakeholder Groups in Göbel et al. (2017)

Examples of stakeholder types identified by interviewees	Internal Stakeholders form part of the immediate project team and research process(es)	External Stakeholders are not considered part of the immediate project team and research process(es), yet have a vested interest in the project
Actual Stakeholders that are currently or have been involved with a CS project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partners/collaborators setting the research question in a collegial project. • University researchers leading and analyzing data from their contributory CS project. • Government department selecting location for CS activity. • NGO hosting a community lab. • Neighbor committee or community members disseminating project findings. • High-school students doing CS as part of their coursework. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SciStarter using CS project metadata. • Atlas of Living Australia making CS data accessible. • Volunteers in a contributory project analyzing data. • Local business informing customers on CS activity. • Schools using CS activities in formal education.
Potential Stakeholders that have not been involved with a CS project, yet could be in the future	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Federal and state agencies funding project and using CS data. • Special interest group participating in knowledge generation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • US health agency using CS data; Australian scientist and "other researchers" using CS data.

This is an important differentiation to also explore in the case of the stakeholders in EU-Citizen.Science. In our case, the actual internal stakeholders are clearly the members of the Consortium and the Third-Party Partners, and their staff. Potential internal stakeholders, could be seen to be those in the wider CS community with whom we are actively collaborating to gather inputs during this first assessment phase and subsequent requirements gathering phase.

3.5 Primary and secondary stakeholders

In the corporate stakeholder literature, an additional difference is made between primary stakeholders, who are essential to the survival and wellbeing of the organization (such as shareholders, employees, customers and those with regulatory authority over the business), and secondary stakeholders, with whom the business interacts but who are not essential to its survival^{22 23}.

It is feels easy to identify who the primary stakeholders of the Platform would be in our case, but it would be risky for us to relegate other stakeholders to the secondary category, because they are often exactly the under-reached groups that we wish to actively engage with via the Project. However, it *is* necessary to prioritise our energies on where they are likely to have the most impact on the success of the Platform, and so we do undertake a prioritisation exercise - but without categorising stakeholders as primary or secondary.

3.6 Stakeholder characterisation

The goal of stakeholder characterisation, as described in Walton et al 2013, is to understand who your stakeholders are as people - what their interests and affiliations are, and the best approaches for communicating with and engaging them over the long term.²⁴

Spending the time to understand the different agenda and reasons that individual stakeholders might have for engaging, and the broad range of educational backgrounds and experience that they might bring to participation, are two key elements that they highlight for the successful planning of engagement strategies by the managers of any project.

Other aspects to consider, as shown in Figure 7 below, include the power and influence that stakeholders might wield over the decision-making process.

Figure 7: Principles for Stakeholder Characterisation. Walton et al, 2013.

²² Freeman RE. 1984. Strategic management: a stakeholder approach. Boston, MA: Pitman

²³ Clarkson MBE. 1995. A stakeholder framework for analyzing and evaluating corporate social performance. Academy of Management Review 20(1): 92-117

²⁴ Walton et al, 2013.

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As the Project progresses, we will continue to flesh out the Stakeholder Register with additional characterisation details that will allow us to engage effectively at key moments of the Project lifecycle.

4. Literature Review: Stakeholder Categories

Similarly to [Section 4](#) above, here we summarise literature that provides us with guidance for identifying and mapping our stakeholders.

4.1 International citizen science stakeholder analysis on data interoperability.

In their exploratory study of citizen science stakeholders involved in data and knowledge generation and the use and reuse of information, Göbel et al. (2017)²⁵ conducted semi-structured interviews with 16 citizen science projects in the USA, Europe and Australia, across a broad spectrum of stakeholders who engage in project decision-making, provide support, and/or use project data. Through this, they identified six main stakeholder groups across the different levels of engagement:

1. Civil society organisations, informal groups and community members;
2. Academic and research organisations;
3. Government agencies and departments;
4. Individual volunteers;
5. Formal learning institutions for primary and secondary education; and
6. Businesses or industry.

Amongst their main findings was the observation that lack of awareness of the project continues to form a real barrier to the involvement of a wide range of stakeholders, and that the difficulty for project coordinators in accessing or knowing how to access potential stakeholders also forms a significant barrier to involvement. This may result in key stakeholder groups remaining un-identified.

In their closing recommendations to the field and future research, Göbel et al (2017) point out that other important external stakeholders may include citizen science data repositories, project databases and practitioner associations.

We note in particular from this publication, that the EU-Citizen.Science stakeholder groupings illustrated in [Figure 4](#) above, do not clearly include civil society organisations, which we will address in [Section 6](#) below..

4.2 The value of stakeholder mapping to enhance co-creation in CS initiatives

The ‘Doing It Together science’ (DITOs) project conducted an in-depth stakeholder mapping workshop of three of their co-creation initiatives, where participants identified the stakeholder

²⁵ Göbel, C., Martin, V.Y. and Ramirez-Andreotta, M., 2017. Stakeholder Analysis: International Citizen Science Stakeholder Analysis on Data Interoperability. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson International Centre for Scholars. Available at <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/international-citizen-science-stakeholder-analysis>

groups involved and discussed the lessons derived from identifying actual and potential stakeholders in different phases of each activity.

For example, the Science Bus project identified six stakeholder groups: (1) local community institutions; (2) local grassroots and frugal innovation groups; (3) facilitators (including bus drivers); (4) local governments; (5) exhibition designers; and (6) DITOs partners, who provide connections to other groups, locations, and help among other contributions.²⁶

The main conclusions from their two-day workshop are contained in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Overview of purposes, characteristics of the mapping process, and major insights for three case studies.

Cases	Co-lab workshop	ITN project	Science Bus
Purpose of stakeholder mapping	Improving activity through reflection & good practice; support replication.	Reflection on pilot phase and anticipatory perspective for project planning.	Project planning to increasing impact during activity’s design stage
Characteristics of mapping	Retrospective mapping. Initially, stakeholders were actual individuals, who were then grouped in categories (i.e., Civil Society, Researchers, Facilitators, and Participants).	Mix of retro- and prospective mapping. Knowledge of past enables detailed mapping for desired future activity.	Prospective mapping. A much more generic categorization of stakeholders (e.g., local grassroots communities) than the previous two cases
Major insights	Identification of extra participants to be included in workshops (e.g., policy makers) and methodological perspectives, e.g., improve stakeholder communication of results.	Influence and interest of stakeholders should inform prioritisation of resources for their engagement. Who should be involved when in the project?	Reflection on desired impacts (engagement & knowledge creation) for the attainment and exploration of engagement strategies based on stakeholder expectations

4.3 The social context of CS Projects

In order to better the perspective of various stakeholders during the project design process, Tiago, 2017 clusters them into four main groups: citizen scientists, scientists, other societal groups and policy makers, as shown in Figure 8 below.

“Citizen scientists and scientists are directly involved in the scientific process, while other societal groups and policy makers are more indirectly involved, e.g. using data, promoting education, guiding policy goals

²⁶ Skarlatidou et al, 2019.

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and decisions or giving answers to social concerns. Assuring a good and stable relationship between the interests of these groups is important for the project's success²⁷.

Figure 8: Groups of Stakeholders involved in Citizen Science projects - Tiago 2017

Tiago’s finding is that clustering a range of stakeholder groups together in this way aids the design of the project’s social context, determining the target audience & recruitment method, developing communication approaches, and understanding the motivation of participants (as shown in Table 4 below). These form a valuable input for our own stakeholder engagement planning, based on our stakeholder map and prioritisation of stakeholders.

Table 4. Project Design points to take into consideration for different stakeholder groups, in a citizen science project design

Project design			
Citizen Scientists	Scientists	Other Societal Groups	Policy Makers
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicating and recruiting participants • Motivating participants • Promoting education • Giving feedback • Enabling personal recognition and reward • Taking into account work scale preference 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enabling outputs for scientific studies • Assuring data quality • Sharing open source results • Fostering innovation, interdisciplinarity and group dynamics • Motivating participants • Overcoming reluctance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giving answers to social concerns • Promoting healthy habits • Promoting inclusion • Promoting awareness and education • Taking into consideration cultural differences • Overcoming reluctance • Sharing open source results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guiding policy goals and decisions • Giving answers to social concerns • Promoting awareness • Overcoming reluctance
Project Evaluation and Governance			

²⁷ Tiago, Patricia. "Social context of citizen science projects." Analyzing the Role of Citizen Science in Modern Research. IGI Global, 2017. 168-191.

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4.4 The European citizen science landscape – a snapshot

A survey of 174 citizen science projects within Europe by Hecker et al. (2018)²⁸ found that approximately 1.2 million people participated in these. The survey also found that, among the projects surveyed, activity is highest in the UK, Germany and Austria; that projects range from international to local in scale; and that the life sciences dominate thematically.

In terms of the organisations coordinating these projects, science organisations dominate (45%), followed by educational organisations (14%) and NGOs (11%). The authors also note that communication in citizen science projects in the EU is mostly conducted in the respective national language, in contrast to the citizen science movements in Australia and the USA (where English is a common shared language) – and this may be a factor behind participants' preference for national-level projects.

This highlights the importance of considering native-language groups when mapping the stakeholder categories, as a tangible and distinct subset of actors. Local language support is an important consideration for the design of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform as well, to be picked up in our assessment of user requirements.

4.5 Citizen science for environmental policy

A report commissioned by the European Commission Directorate-General for Environment (DG-Env)²⁹ presents the findings from a desk-study and survey of citizen science projects and citizen observatories across Europe, which found 503 projects (as of February 2018) that can or do have an impact on environmental policy decision making. Among these, the authors noted efforts to develop infrastructure, strategies and platforms for citizen science in Scotland and the UK, Germany and France. They also identified Europe-wide initiatives, such as the Interest Group on Citizen Science of the European Network of Environmental Protection Agencies (Bio Innovation Service, 2018).³⁰

This study included the collection of tens of meta portals that can be used again to refine the initial search of players, including at macro-regional levels: Cordis H2020, DG Env, EEA, JRC, CAPS, Open Science Monitor, COST Action, Living Knowledge, ENOLL; at national level, Spain, Austria, Switzerland, Germany, Australia, United States, France, Latvia, New Zealand, Ireland and Sweden. Other portals include Zooniverse, OpenStreetmap, BOINC, etc.

We note that the EU-Citizen.Science stakeholder categories illustrated in [Figure 4](#) above, do not sufficiently account for the sister CS associations, networks and platforms that will undoubtedly be stakeholders in the Project. We therefore expand in them further in [Section 6](#) below.

²⁸ Hecker, S., Garbe, L. and Bonn, A. (2018) 'The European citizen science landscape – a snapshot', pp. 190-200 in Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. and Bonn, A. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London.

²⁹ Bio Innovation Service (2018) *Citizen science for environmental policy: development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices*. Final report for the European Commission, DG Environment under the contract 070203/2017/768879/ETU/ENV.A.3, in collaboration with Fundacion Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum. European Union, Brussels.

³⁰ Bio Innovation Service (2018) *Citizen science for environmental policy: development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices*. Final report for the European Commission, DG Environment under the contract 070203/2017/768879/ETU/ENV.A.3, in collaboration with Fundacion Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum. European Union, Brussels.

5 Collaborative Stakeholder Workshops

As noted in our methodology, we strive to be as collaborative as possible throughout the Project, and have thus also gathered the inputs of the wider community via a series of collaborative workshops with key stakeholders. A longer summary of each are contained in the Appendices to this deliverable.

5.1 Pre-Proposal Workshop in Berlin, 28 February 2018

During the proposal preparation phase, ECSA invited all who expressed interest in the topic of the H2020 Coordination and Support Action (CSA) Call to participate in a collective co-creative process to define the structure and content of the Platform, and the relevant stakeholders across the field of citizen science in Europe.

To this end, a workshop was held in Berlin on the 28th of February 2018, hosted by ECSA and the Museum für Naturkunde, with 24 attendees from 10 countries taking part (see [Appendix 4](#) below for a longer write-up). A full-group session was run to identify the relevant stakeholder groups, which were identified as being:

1. The general public (including citizen scientists, NGOs and CSOs),
2. Academia (including career scientists),
3. Educators (including primary and secondary school teachers),
4. Policy makers and regulatory authorities in the field of environment, city planning, etc.,
5. Science journalists and science media , and
6. Industry and SMEs

This is the source of the main actor groups illustrated at the outset of this Report, in [Figure 4](#).

The groupings of core users of the EU-Citizen.Science platform that emerged from the subsequent break-out group discussions took a slightly different shape, as shown in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9: Initial stakeholder map for the EU-Citizen.Science Platform

In describing and assessing these Platform user groups, the workshop participants noted that they should include the following:

- Currently active actors in citizen science, as well as newcomers
- Decision makers and users of citizen science based data or solutions.
- Multiple types of users of citizen science guidelines, tools and materials - from those inexperienced, to citizens and scientists who already engage in citizen science activities
- Multiple users of best practice examples and relevant scientific outcomes, ranging from interested citizens through scientific institutions to politicians and the media.
- Members of the public - the citizen scientists themselves
- Those who are inexperienced in organising and supporting citizen science initiatives, and not necessarily trained in scientific practices.

These user groupings are developed and presented in more detail within Deliverable 2.2 *'Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan'*, and Deliverable 2.3 *'Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report'*. Here, they form a valuable input to the Stakeholder Register shared in [Section 6.7](#) below.

5.2. COST Action WG2 Workshop in Brussels, 1-2 April 2019

The workshop entitled *'Building a community network for educators, teachers, Citizen Science practitioners and researchers on synergies between Citizen Science and Education'* was organised and run by members of the Citizen Science COST Action CA15212 Working Group 2 *'Education'*, in collaboration with ECSA and other project partners. (See [Appendix 5](#) below for a longer write-up).

The main goal of the workshop was to effectively and sustainably connect the diverse stakeholders in the field of Citizen Science and Education by contributing to the development of: a) a platform that enables us to easily share existing resources and to collaborate openly on creating new ones, and b) a communication strategy that is tailored to the stakeholders' needs.

Participants at the workshop came from nine different countries and represented teachers, educators, scientists, citizen science researchers, national hubs, the Citizen Science COST Action, the European Citizen Science Association, and EU-Citizen.Science.

The four categories of potential platform users that the group chose to focus on were

1. Teachers,
2. Science educators / Scientists,
3. CS participants, and
4. Informal educators.

The group then discussed the characteristics of each identified persona, the expected pathway into the network, some of the key barriers to engagement, and possible solutions. These will form a key input to the Deliverable 2.3 *'Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report'*.

At the end of this second session, time was taken to identify actors who were not represented by the personas selected, and their relation to the proposed citizen science community network. These were, determined by category:

- Higher Education
 - Public engagement departments

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- University professionals
- Degree programmes
- Initial teacher education
- Teacher Leadership
 - Head of Department
 - Headteachers
 - Local Authority
- Other Education
 - Parent associations
 - Home school networks
 - Museum educators
- Programme/project managers within organisations
 - Government organisations (National Parks, Forestry etc)
 - Civic organisations (libraries, community hubs)
 - Non-profit/NGOs
- Media
 - Mainstream journalism
 - Social media influencers
- Policy Makers
 - Educational policy makers
 - Environmental/planning policy makers
- Trade Unions
- Wider community members
 - Retired/elderly people (often have time/money or come with young people)
 - Young people directly (not through formal/informal learning mechanisms)³¹

The outputs of this workshop thus form a very valuable breakdown of the sub-groups contained within our overarching stakeholder groupings, which we include in the Stakeholder Register contained in [Section 6.7](#) below.

5.3. Joint Workshop with COST Action WG4 in Brussels, 10-11 April 2019

The workshop entitled ‘*Co-creating the European citizen science platform of the future*’ was organised by ECSA in co-operation with the Museum für Naturkunde (MfN) and the members of the Citizen Science COST Action CA15212 Working Group 4 ‘*Enhance the role of CS for civil society*’. It had the dual aim of actively contributing to the collaborative development of the Platform, and identifying potential collaborations between the ongoing COST Action and the Platform, throughout its development.

The 18 participants from 11 countries in attendance were invited to share their expectations for the platform, and to contribute their expertise by identifying potential features and functionalities. (See [Appendix 6](#) for a longer write-up)

As well as informing the Stakeholder Identification, the outcomes of this workshop are highly valuable inputs to the Deliverable 2.3 ‘*Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report*’.

³¹ Lorke 2019

The EU-Citizen.Science Stakeholders

6. Stakeholder Identification

The first step in any stakeholder mapping process is to take an iterative and ‘living document’ approach, such that it is not static, but can be adapted as the project develops, and our engagement objectives change.

Building on the first brainstorming session that took place in Berlin on the 28th of February 2018, as described above in [Section 3](#), we now conduct a quick ‘sense-check’ of which stakeholders might have been missed, by looking at a classic stakeholder category list, as shown in Table 5 below:

Table 5: A ‘sense-check’ of the EU-Citizen.Science stakeholders against a classic stakeholder list

Classic stakeholder categories ³²	EU-Citizen.Science stakeholders
Owners - investors, shareholders, agents, analysts, and ratings agencies	Our funders - the Project Officer, EC-DG ENV, JRC, EASME, etc
Customers - direct customers, indirect customers, and advocates	Platform users - those who will seek tools, guidelines, materials, and community contacts/interaction - and contribute the same
Employees - current employees, potential employees, retirees, representatives, and dependents	Project members - the consortium partners, third party partners, and their staff
Industry - suppliers, competitors, industry associations, industry opinion leaders, and media	Toolmakers - SMEs and others. Related Scientific Associations (such as BES), CS Associations (such as ACSA), CS Platforms (such as SciStarter), Science Media
Community - residents near company facilities, chambers of commerce, resident associations, schools, community organizations, and special interest groups	The community of CS practitioners - the members of ECSA, ACSA, CSA, CSGP, the CS COST Action, etc
Environment - nature, nonhuman species, future generations, scientists, ecologists, spiritual communities, advocates, and NGOs	*the outcomes of many CS projects have an impact on the actors named here, so indirectly the Platform will as well
Government - public authorities, and local policymakers; regulators; and opinion leaders	Also government bodies, public authorities, local policymakers, and national regulators
Civil society organizations - NGOs, faith-based organizations, and labor unions	Also CSOs, NGOs and other organisations focused on the public good

³² BSR Stakeholder Mapping, Nov 2011 <https://www.bsr.org/>

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Returning again to the overarching stakeholder groupings presented in [Figure 4](#) above, we now start to break out these groupings into more nuanced detail, address the stakeholder groups we have identified as not yet clearly represented, and bring together the gathered inputs in a more structured fashion.

6.1 Academia

Academia, or ‘Scientists’ is the catch-all category usually used to describe professional practitioners of the citizen science method, but a number of groups clearly fit into this category. We therefore breakout ‘Academia’ further to explicitly include:

- Universities
- University departments
- University research groups
- Research Institutions
- Institutional research groups
- Companies conducting scientific research
- Museums
- Science Shops

The typical roles fulfilled within this category include designing and running citizen science projects, verifying and analysing the data collected by citizen scientists, improving the rigour of methodologies, publishing CS outcomes, and steering CS projects towards new or important areas of study.

The second principle of citizen science (ECSA, 2015) states that both professional scientists and citizens should benefit from participation through “*the publication of research outputs, learning opportunities, personal enjoyment, social benefits, satisfaction from contributing to scientific evidence ... and ... the potential to influence policy*”.³³

However, not all professionals within the sub-categories named above currently engage with the sector, or take advantage of the opportunities that the CS method offers. The stated aim of EU-Citizen.Science is to provide a range of tools, resources and networking opportunities to:

- Raise awareness of the potential benefits of CS projects, and communicate findings
- Share existing CS tools, methodologies and training modules
- Offer a place to share and promote those resources that professional scientists create themselves
- Provide signposts to CS-derived datasets that may be of use to their own research.

We therefore note that the people who work at organisations in this category and its sub-groups will range in experience from new to CS, to active practitioner. It is therefore necessary to define further who the people within these groups might be.

- Universities
 - Professors
 - Researchers (from Jr. to Senior, including PostDocs)
 - Lecturers
 - PhD students
 - Masters and Undergraduate Students

³³ https://ecsa.citizen-science.net/sites/default/files/ecsa_ten_principles_of_citizen_science.pdf

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- University departments
- Department Heads
- University research groups
 - Research Group Leads
 - Principal Investigators
- Research Institutions
 - Senior Management
 - Department Heads
 - Research Group Leads
 - Principal Investigators
 - Researchers (from Jr. to Senior, including PostDocs)
 - Staff
- Museums
 - Science Directors
 - Research Group Leads
 - Principal Investigators
 - Researchers (from Jr. to Senior, including PostDocs)
 - Project Managers
 - Project Staff
- Science Shops
 - Science Shop Coordinators
 - Science Shop Staff

We furthermore note that people who fill the role of researcher, irregardless of the organisation or level of experience, might be either conducting their research within a specific domain, or researching ‘The Science of Citizen Science’.

Many European CS projects, particularly those that have been funded by the European Commission via the FP7 or H2020 funding programmes, are run by consortia of partners that include organisations and individuals in the above-named categories. For the purposes of this stakeholder mapping exercise we take the view that although CS projects may very well be positively impacted by the successful launch of the EU-Citizen.Science Platform, it is the consortia members who are the stakeholders, not the project itself. (Especially as these projects are not a legal entity).

6.2 The Public - i.e. Citizen Scientists

Similarly to ‘Academia’, ‘the Public’ is also a catch-all phrase used to indicate the participants (and potential participants) in citizen science projects, who do not need to be academically or scientifically trained in order to take part. We are careful not to insinuate that ‘the Public’ are not scientists, as in fact there are quite a few examples of people with scientific training making volunteer contributions in their own time (for example, to the GBIF database of nature observations³⁴). Rather, the term seeks to indicate people acting in a non-professional capacity.

It is clear that this category requires breaking out into a larger number sub-groups, but this poses a challenge, because we are all individual members of the public when we take off our professional ‘hats’. The Public can thus include:

³⁴ Chandler, Mark, et al. "Contribution of citizen science towards international biodiversity monitoring." *Biological Conservation* 213 (2017): 280-294.

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- Residents in a local community
- Members of an interest group or community group
- Primary and Secondary school students
- Hobbyists and amateur experts
- Anyone interested in an issue, research question, or domain of research

This view of the public focuses on those who participate in CS as citizen scientists, as well as those who could potentially participate in CS in the future. However, if we switch focus to those who design, launch and run citizen science projects in a non-professional capacity (also known as DIY, grassroots, or bottom-up CS), then we can include organisational actors as well individual actors. These might be:

- Local community groups
- Community centres
- Special interest groups
- Activist groups
- Charities
- Libraries

Conceivably, this sub-set might also include "quasi-autonomous non-governmental organisations", or quangos, which are non-governmental organisations that perform functions that would usually be governmental functions, and receive funding or other forms of support from the government.

6.3 Where to place CSOs and NGOs?

We now raise the question of where to place Civic Society Organisations (CSOs) and Non-governmental Organisations (NGOs). Both can be seen to be occupying the public space as non-profit organisations, and yet they are indeed professional organisations and their involvement in CS is typically in a professional capacity, as CS project leaders, partners or supporters.

NGOs are key actors in citizen science, particularly in the environmental, social and humanitarian sectors. NGOs often collaborate with academic institutions; others are well positioned to understand specific policy needs, whether at local or broader geographical scale, and give them an effective voice. They are also effective in reaching potential participants, harnessing broad stakeholder support, and securing funding from various private and non-governmental sources.³⁵

Examples of NGOs that are already crucial stakeholders in the EU-Citizen.Science platform, include consortium partners ECSA, Earthwatch, and Ecsite. Both ECSA and Ecsite are in fact membership organisations. We can thus also include other CS membership associations in this category, such as the CSA, ACSA, the Asian CS Network, and the CS Global Partnership. However in listing them here, we note that the members of these associations most commonly fit the description of 'Academia'.

This raises the further question of whether to include CS networks here as well, such as the Austrian Österreich Forscht platform, BürGer schaffen WISSen in Germany, the Spanish

³⁵ Bio Innovation Service (2018) *Citizen science for environmental policy: development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices*. Final report for the European Commission, DG Environment under the contract 070203/2017/768879/ETU/ENV.A.3, in collaboration with Fundacion Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum. European Union, Brussels.

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Observatory of Citizen Science, the Swedish Citizen Science portal, and the Citizen Science action in Ireland.

A much broader and inclusive grouping is the ‘civil society organizations’ or CSOs.

“[CSOs] can be defined to include all non-market and non-state organizations outside of the family in which people organize themselves to pursue shared interests in the public domain. Examples include community-based organizations and village associations, environmental groups, women’s rights groups, farmers’ associations, faith-based organizations, labour unions, co-operatives, professional associations, chambers of commerce, independent research institutes and the not-for-profit media.”³⁶

CSOs are thus voluntary organizations with governance and direction coming from citizens or constituency members, without significant government-controlled participation or representation.

The list of stakeholders within the broader CSO category would thus include:

- NGOs
- Citizen Science Associations
- Museum Associations
- Science Communications Associations
- Citizen Science Networks

If we add to this list the bodies that make up the OECD’s definition of a CSO, we find many community-based organisations that we considered to fall under ‘the Public’ such as:

- community-based organizations
- village associations,
- environmental groups,
- women’s rights groups,
- farmers’ associations,
- Faith-based organizations,
- labour unions,
- co-operatives,
- professional associations,
- chambers of commerce,

To solve this, we make the distinction that CSOs with a formal organisation structure or legal status fall within this CSO category, and otherwise we consider them to fall under ‘the Public’.

Having raised the question of where to place NGOs and CSOs in our ‘bubble’ of core stakeholder groupings, as depicted in Figure 4 above, it is clear that we have identified another major category that is worth listing separately.

³⁶ 2007–2008 WorldBank Advisory Group on CSOs and Aid Effectiveness. <http://siteresources.worldbank.org/ACCRAEXT/Resources/4700790-1208545462880/AG-CS-Synthesis-of-Findings-and-Recommendations.pdf>

Figure 12: Our first revision of the main stakeholder groupings

6.4 Educators (Formal and Informal)

This category is our first expansion beyond the four groupings of the Quadruple Helix model, as described in [Section 3.1](#) above. In the introductory text of the EU-Citizen.Science proposal, ‘Educators’ are clearly stated as a key stakeholder target group for our 3rd objective to “Empower diverse stakeholders to become citizen scientists, start citizen science initiatives, and adopt citizen science approaches professionally”. Educators are mentioned again in the description of WP5, which states that

*“The training will be designed for four target groups, which are noted in the call text: public (newcomers and citizen scientists), practitioners (coordinators), academia (career scientists, **primary and secondary school teachers**), policy makers (and civil servants), press (journalists and media experts), and SMEs and industry (and new entrepreneurs),*

and in WP6, which states

*“To reach these objectives the WP will disseminate the results of the project to key audiences following the quadruple helix stakeholder approach, such as policymakers, intermediaries, researchers, practitioners, journalists, **educators**, citizen scientists, science communicators, and citizens”*

It is important to make a clear distinction between tertiary education in ‘Academia’, and earlier levels of education in this ‘Educators’ category. The formal education system - notably primary and secondary schools - provides a unique opportunity to engage young people in citizen science, thus enlivening and enriching science learning, promoting STEM³⁷ careers from a gender-inclusive perspective, and broadening the scope of the research by including a greater range of perspectives (Makuch and Aczel, 2018).³⁸

The students in this case are the citizen scientists within any given project, and are thus covered in the category of ‘the Public’. Here, our focus is on the educators who are introducing CS into the curriculum, classroom enrichment, extra-curricular activities, or other formal and informal learning contexts.

The list for this category, drawing in part from the COST Action workshop described in [Section 5.2](#) above, includes:

- Educators
 - Primary teachers
 - Secondary teachers
 - Club leaders and other extracurricular leaders (e.g. Science Clubs, Scouts)
 - Museum education and learning staff
 - NGO/CSO education and learning staff (e.g. National Parks)
 - Informal learning leaders
- Education Leadership
 - Heads of Department
 - Headteachers
 - Local Authorities
 - Museum education programme coordinators

³⁷ Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics. This is sometimes extended to STEMM, with the final letter representing Medicine.

³⁸ Makuch, K.E. and Aczel, M.R. (2018) ‘Children and citizen science’, pp. 391-409 in Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. and Bonn, A. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London.

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- NGO/CSO education programme coordinators
- Museums
 - Public Engagement & Learning Directors
 - Public Engagement & Learning Staff
- Other Education
 - Parent associations
 - Home school networks

6.4 Policy Makers (and Funding Bodies)

The ‘Policy Makers’ category of stakeholders is an important one, not due to our expectations of their active involvement in the Project, but due to the potential impact of improved communications flows about the benefits of CS on our stated goal of mainstreaming CS in Europe.

By contributing to evidence-based policy, citizen science can contribute to solving societal challenges, increasing sustainability and improving governance at local, national and European levels. But bridging the gap between research and policy is notoriously difficult, and this is no different for citizen scientists. During a survey of citizen science for environmental policy (Bio Innovation Service, 2018),³⁹ only 27% of respondents knew of their project data being used for policy evaluation, while only 16% of projects effectively contributed to policy compliance. While these figures highlight the difficulty in linking citizen science research to policy, it also represents an opportunity for EU-Citizen.Science: if the platform can reach policymakers effectively, then this will help to overcome this significant barrier. Additionally, Bio Innovation Service (2018) found that while in some cases policy links are planned from the outset, in many instances they are an afterthought, or simply correspond to an unintended use. While not all projects should – or indeed want to – link to policy, there is clearly a need for links to be forged with this stakeholder group and the others.

Policymakers are not, however, a clearly delineated group. Policy evolves in various ways in different sectors and at different levels, with the actors involved also varying in each case, both in typology and their level of input/involvement. For example, policymaking not only involves those who sign off on the final policy document (the decision-maker), but those that advise, inform and influence them throughout the process. In the first persona-mapping exercise for the concept of a CS platform for Europe, the Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) identified seven potential user types for this platform⁴⁰:

1. Decision-makers
2. Policy officers
3. Thematic experts
4. Project managers
5. Application developers
6. Spectators
7. Active citizens

³⁹ Bio Innovation Service (2018) *Citizen science for environmental policy: development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices*. Final report for the European Commission, DG Environment under the contract 070203/2017/768879/ETU/ENV.A.3, in collaboration with Fundacion Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum. European Union, Brussels.

⁴⁰ Schade S, Fullerton K, Tsinaraki C, et al. (2016) *Citizen Science Platform - Architecture Document; JRC103171*. European Union, Brussels.

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While the latter two are covered in ‘the Public’, the first five items on this list help to unpack the concept of policy-making into specific roles beyond a government official or member of parliament, to include other key stakeholders in the policy-making process.

This raises the question of where to include funding bodies - most particularly, the funding body behind this Project - as highlighted in the ‘sense-check’ exercise in [Table 9](#) above. We reach the conclusion that they also fit here in the Policy Maker category, and thus expand the list to include:

- The Horizon 2020 Research Framework Programme of the European Commission
- The European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation (DG-RI)
- The European Commission Directorate-General for the Environment (DG-Env)
- The EC Joint Research Centre (JRC)
- The SwafS Programme
- The EU-Citizen.Science Project Officer
- The Executive Agency for Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (EASME)

As noted in [Section 1.3](#) above, a more granular identification of policy stakeholders at the national and local level will be performed in Task 4.1 of the Project, which will produce a set of policy recommendations on how to make use of and support citizen science, facilitating:

1. communication of information needs;
2. partnership between policy makers and citizen scientists;
3. joint planning and fundraising;
4. engagement of policy makers in citizen science;
5. establishment of a research ethics;
6. motivation of collaboration;
7. identification and production of key messages and recommendations;
8. discussion between policy makers and citizen scientists;
9. production of supporting materials; and
10. capacity building.

6.5 The Press (and the Science Media)

Our second deviation from the Quadruple Helix model, as shown in [Figure 3.1](#) above, is to split out the Press & Media from the Public and civil society. The Press - particularly science journalists and science media such as science magazines (e.g. *New Scientist*), blogs (e.g. *IFL Science*), radio and TV programmes, podcasts (e.g. *The Naked Scientist*) and social media channels dedicated to promoting science - has an important role to play in communicating the benefits and successes of citizen science, which should support efforts to increase the number of people participating in projects. They also offer professional scientists with an avenue to disseminate their research outcomes beyond peer-reviewed books and journals, potentially bringing these to new audiences or strengthening the message for existing ones (i.e. policymakers).

The Platform has the potential to be an important source of news and stories for the science media, or a place to find contacts for citizen science practitioners to be interviewed for an article or programme. It will be important to ensure that they can find the right content and contacts easily on the platform, and know what can and cannot be reproduced.

Actors in this category may have a clear interest in the Platform, but are less likely to feel like they have a stake in its success, nor will they have a strong influence over its success. We nonetheless consider them to be one of our target audiences, as defined in our mission.

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6.6 Industry (and SMEs, and Technology providers)

Although industrial organisations can often be identified as stakeholders in specific CS initiatives, such as odour-emitting industries within the D-Noses project⁴¹, there are surprisingly few references to the role of Industry in CS beyond the provision of technical tools, such as smartphones and sensors. Göbel et al. (2017)⁴² also found that industry and business involvement was absent in the large majority of citizen science projects, being more deeply involved in co-created projects, where they assisted decision-making, provided support, and used the data and knowledge.

Within the community of CS practitioners known to the Project consortium, there are a number of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) actors who are active participants in other CS consortia, or who build mobile applications and web platforms specifically for use in CS initiatives. We consider these to be active CS practitioners who are not adequately described in the categories above, and so this Industry & SME category is an important one.

The involvement of industry and including new startups, in citizen science projects can bring a number of benefits. These businesses can use the data created by citizen science initiatives, leading to social innovation and the creation of jobs, among other benefits. However, This group is broad and somewhat disparate - the industries that are relevant or interested will depend largely on the nature of the citizen science project. It is tempting to therefore remove this category from our core list of stakeholders, however doing so would both break the logic of the Quadruple Helix model, and also cause us to miss a range of SMEs that are very active in the field: such as Spotteron, Techiu, ONSubject, and more.

This category can also include the developers of technical tools, software, mobile & web apps and web platforms, sensors and other hardware in a commercial setting, for example ESRI and Open Street Map. Some of these may cross-over into CSO territory due to their non-profit status, however we chose to list them here in order to highlight their technology-tool oriented nature.

6.7 The Resulting Stakeholder Categories

In conclusion to the above identification of stakeholder categories, sub-groups and organisational or individual actors, we add an additional 'bubble' to our illustration of the Stakeholder groupings within EU-Citizen.Science, as illustrated in Figure 10 below.

⁴¹ <https://dnoses.eu/2019/07/22/international-odour-observatory/>

⁴² Göbel, C., Martin, V.Y. and Ramirez-Andreotta, M., 2017. Stakeholder Analysis: International Citizen Science Stakeholder Analysis on Data Interoperability. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson International Centre for Scholars. Available at <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/international-citizen-science-stakeholder-analysis>

Figure 10: Updated stakeholder groupings within EU-Citizen.Science

7 The Stakeholder Register

Having established the methodology for our stakeholder analysis exercise, and identified the stakeholder categories and sub-groups, we now enter the collaborative input gathering phase that will continue throughout the life of the project, to be captured in ‘living documents’ that can guide the work of the consortium partners across all work packages.

By definition, these elements of the deliverable are not locked down. Rather, they will continue to be added to and fleshed out as we continue to gather inputs from key actors regarding stakeholders, users, our target audience, and their requirements - within the WP2 tasks, as well as other WP tasks across the full Project timeline.

The outcomes are captured in the [Stakeholder Register](#), which we maintain online in a shared Google Drive folder. The Stakeholder Register as of 30 September 2019 is included in this document as [Appendix 1](#) below.

Figure 11: Screenshot of the Stakeholder Register

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STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SUB-CATEGORY	ORGANISATIONAL STAKEHOLDER	INDIVIDUAL STAKEHOLDER(S)
Internal Stakeholder	Consortium Partner	Museum für Naturkunde	Katrin Vohland, Katherin Wagenknecht
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	European Citizen Science Association	Johannes Vogel, Dorte Riemenschneider, Marzia Mazzonetto, Margaret Gold, Tim Woods
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	IIASA	Dilek Fraisl, Steffen Fritz, Gerid Hager
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	Earthwatch	Luigi Ceccaroni, Mollie Latham
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	ZSI	Barbara Kieslinger, Teresa Schäfer
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	University College London (UCL)	Muki Haklay, Christian Nold, Alice Sheppard
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	ECSITE	Maria Zolotonosa, Lucie Stejgleder
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	Trinity College Dublin (TCD)	Joseph Roche, Laura Bell,
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	Vetenskap & Allmanhet (VA)	Frederik Brouneus,
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	the Natural History Museum (NHM)	Jessica Wardlaw, Lucy Robinson
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	Universiteit Leiden (UL)	Matthijs Begheyn, Pedro Russo, Frans Snik, Anne Land, Liselotte Rambonnet
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	Mykolo Romerio University (MRU)	Monika Mačiulienė, Eglė Marija Ramanauskaitė
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	The Municipality of De Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo (MFCR)	Maria Inês Vicente
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	The Spanish Ministry of Economics, Industry and Competitiveness (MINECO)	Borja Izquierdo

7.1 Stakeholder Analysis

The stakeholder analysis is contained in [the second tab of the living Stakeholder Register](#), which will be updated throughout the life of the project. The structure of the Shareholder Analysis as of 30 September 2019 is included in this document as [Appendix 2](#) below.

Figure 12: Screenshot of the Stakeholder Analysis

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STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SUB-CATEGORY	ROLE	STAKE IN PROJECT	PREDISPOSITION	INFLUENCE	SUPPORT	INTEREST	IMPACT	ANTICIPATED INVOLVEMENT	BARRIERS
				Current commitment profile: resistant, ambivalent, neutral, supportive/committed	Score out of 5				What level of involvement is expected?	Known or
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	Execution	Financial, professional commitment, reputational, meeting own needs	Committed	5	5	5	5	Direct responsibility	
	Linked Third Party	Input	Reputational, meeting own needs	Committed	5	5	5	5	Full involvement	
	EC Project Officer	Oversight	Reputational, professional commitment	Committed	5	5	5	4	Direct contact with Coordinator, pre-defined review moments	
	Advisory Board	Input	Reputational, meeting own needs	Committed	5	5	5	5	Advice, active engagement and active contribution	

7.2 Stakeholder Mapping

A classic tool of stakeholder analysis (see for example Eden & Ackerman 1988⁴³), the Interest/Influence matrix maps stakeholders and their relation to the Project against four quadrants, providing insights on the importance and influence of each stakeholder.

'Interest' indicates the level of engagement of the stakeholder with the goals of the Project and their desire for the Platform to succeed. 'Influence' indicates their ability to play an active role in its success, such as committing resources. With this information, it becomes possible to develop a specific approach and strategy for the identified stakeholders (as shown in Figure 13 below), and an indication of where to prioritise our communication and engagement efforts.

Figure 13: Activity prioritisation on the Interest/Influence matrix

⁴³ Eden, C. and Ackermann, F. (1998) Making Strategy: The Journey of Strategic Management, London: Sage Publications.

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The placement of stakeholders across the quadrants also provides an indication of their status to the project. The classic interpretation is:

- High Interest & High Influence = the Primary stakeholders
- High Interest or High Influence = the Secondary stakeholders
- Low Interest & Low Influence = the Tertiary stakeholders

Our first mapping of the Stakeholders identified above emphasizes their roles as Users of the Platform and the level of experience that they have in CS, as shown in Figure 14 below.

Figure 14: First draft of the EU-Citizen.Science Interest/Influence matrix

As above, this matrix is also a living document, which can be adjusted for new understanding throughout the life of the project, and can be found [in the third and fourth tabs of the Stakeholder Register](#). The matrices as of 30 September 2019 are included in this document as [Appendix 3](#) below.

7.3 Stakeholder Prioritisation

In this D2.1 ‘*Stakeholders, Network & Community Mapping Report*’, which is the first deliverable within Task 2.1 ‘*Mapping of stakeholders, key networks & platform-community members; multi-level engagement model for community and network building*’, we have established a definition of stakeholders as ‘Any person, group, or entity with a common interest or stake in the outcomes of the Project and the success of the Platform’.

Our methodology has been to identify the relevant stakeholder groups and sub-groups, to analyse these groups in order to understand their interests and influence, and to map these relationships visually. The final step is now to prioritise their relevance to the Project and our efforts to both communicate and engage with them.

Our core aim is to ensure the successful building of the Platform and completion of the Project, and this will ultimately be defined by how much the Users turn to the Platform for useful information and content, and in turn contribute their own tools, guidelines and materials, as well as actively participate in the community forums. The (potential) Users of the Platform are therefore our priority stakeholders.

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As described in [Figure 5](#) above, the two core User groupings for the Platform can be divided into those who are ‘producers’ of Citizen Science, i.e. people who do Citizen Science, and those who are ‘consumers’ of Citizen Science, i.e. those who use the outcomes of Citizen Science. Both groups contain people who are acting in different contexts, and at different levels of experience, from beginner to expert.

To prioritise our efforts and select key stakeholder representatives with whom we engage most closely, a more granular assessment is required, and this is undertaken within the Stakeholder Analysis described in [Section 7.1](#) above. Our engagement strategy with these groups is described in more detail in the D2.2 ‘*Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan*’ submitted in parallel to this Report.

An additional important aim is to ensure the long-term sustainability and longevity of the Platform in the hands of ECSA, who will take on its management beyond the end of the Project. It is therefore important to identify ECSA itself as one of the priority stakeholders in the project, and that the Platform structure must be aligned with ECSA’s ability to maintain and sustain the platform over the long term.

10. Next Steps

Stakeholder identification and analysis is an iterative process, which we will continue throughout the lifetime Project, as we continue to collaborate and engage with stakeholders, and adjust to any changes in the context, the institutional surroundings, or individuals and their respective roles:

“The ‘stakeholder landscape’ is by no means a stable one. It constantly changes according to interests, changes in external conditions, and the different phases of the process”⁴⁴

The Stakeholder Register is thus a living document that will be continuously updated in order to incorporate the perspectives, questions and priorities generated by stakeholders over the course of the Project.

The next steps in Task 2.1 ‘*Mapping of stakeholders, key networks & platform-community members; multi-level engagement model for community and network building*’ are to continue to gather the inputs of the wider CS community, who represent both Stakeholders and Users of the Platform, in order to fill in more of the detail of the Stakeholder Register.

⁴⁴ Zimmermann, A. and C. Maennling. 2007. Mainstreaming Participation: Multi-stakeholder management: Tools for Stakeholder Analysis: 10 Building Blocks for Designing Participatory Systems of Cooperation. Promoting Participatory Development in German Development Cooperation. Eschborn, Germany: Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit (GTZ). <http://www.fsnnetwork.org/sites/default/files/en-svmp-instrumente-akteursanalyse.pdf>

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REFERENCES

Bio Innovation Service (2018) *Citizen science for environmental policy: development of an EU-wide inventory and analysis of selected practices*. Final report for the European Commission, DG Environment under the contract 070203/2017/768879/ETU/ENV.A.3, in collaboration with Fundacion Ibercivis and The Natural History Museum. European Union, Brussels.

Göbel, C., Martin, V.Y. and Ramirez-Andreotta, M., 2017. Stakeholder Analysis: International Citizen Science Stakeholder Analysis on Data Interoperability. Washington, DC: Woodrow Wilson International Centre for Scholars. Available at <https://www.wilsoncenter.org/publication/international-citizen-science-stakeholder-analysis>

Harlin, J., Kloetzer, L., Patton, D., Leonhard, C. and Leysin American School high school students (2018) 'Turning students into citizen scientists', pp. 410-428 in Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. and Bonn, A. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London.

Hecker, S., Garbe, L. and Bonn, A. (2018) 'The European citizen science landscape – a snapshot', pp. 190-200, in Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. and Bonn, A. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London.

Lelea, M.A., G.M. Roba, A. Christinck, B. Kaufmann. 2014. Methodologies for stakeholder analysis – for application in transdisciplinary research projects focusing on actors in food supply chains. German Institute for Tropical and Subtropical Agriculture (DITSL). Witzenhausen, Germany.

Lorke, J. and Rushton, E. (2019) 'Building a community network for educators, teachers, Citizen Science practitioners and researchers on synergies between Citizen Science and Education: Vision & personas'. Workshop report, COST Action WG2. Brussels, 1-2 April 2019. Unpublished.

Makuch, K.E. and Aczel, M.R. (2018) 'Children and citizen science', pp. 391-409 in Hecker, S., Haklay, M., Bowser, A., Makuch, Z., Vogel, J. and Bonn, A. *Citizen Science: Innovation in Open Science, Society and Policy*. UCL Press, London.

Schade S, Fullerton K, Tsinaraki C, et al. (2016) *Citizen Science Platform - Architecture Document; JRC103171*. European Union, Brussels.

Stakeholder Mapping Guide For Conservation International Country Programs & Partners - <https://iwlearn.net/resolveuid/d20fc335-aa29-440b-ac14-f94f37321427>

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Zimmermann, A. and C. Maennling. 2007. Mainstreaming Participation: Multi-stakeholder management: Tools for Stakeholder Analysis: 10 Building Blocks for Designing Participatory Systems of Cooperation. Promoting Participatory Development in German Development Cooperation. Eschborn, Germany: Deutsche Gesellschaft für Technische Zusammenarbeit (GTZ). <http://www.fsnnetwork.org/sites/default/files/en-svmp-instrumente-akteursanalyse.pdf>

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APPENDIX 1 - Stakeholder Register

Work-in-progress as of September 30, 2019 ([Living document online](#))

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STAKEHOLDER GROUP	SUB-CATEGORY	ORGANISATIONAL STAKEHOLDER	INDIVIDUAL STAKEHOLDER(S)
Internal Stakeholders	Consortium Partner	<i>Museum für Naturkunde</i>	Katrin Vohland, Katherin Wagenknecht
	Consortium Partner	<i>European Citizen Science Association</i>	Johannes Vogel, Dorte Riemenschneider, Marzia Mazzonetto, Margaret Gold, Tim Woods
	Consortium Partner	<i>ILASA</i>	Dilek Fraisl, Steffen Fritz, Gerid Hager
	Consortium Partner	<i>Earthwatch</i>	Luigi Ceccaroni, Mollie Latham
	Consortium Partner	<i>ZSI</i>	Barbara Kieslinger, Teresa Schäfer
	Consortium Partner	<i>University College London (UCL)</i>	Muki Haklay, Christian Nold, Alice Sheppard
	Consortium Partner	<i>ECSITE</i>	Maria Zolotonosa, Lucie Steigleder
	Consortium Partner	<i>Trinity College Dublin (TCD)</i>	Joseph Roche, Laura Bell,
	Consortium Partner	<i>Vetenskap & Allmanhet (VA)</i>	Frederik Brouneus,
	Consortium Partner	<i>the Natural History Museum (NHM)</i>	Jessica Wardlaw, Lucy Robinson
	Consortium Partner	<i>Universiteit Leiden (UL)</i>	Matthijs Begheyn, Pedro Russo, Frans Snik, Anne Land, Liselotte Rambonnet
	Consortium Partner	<i>Mykolo Romerio University (MRU)</i>	Monika Mačiulienė, Eglė Marija Ramanauskaitė
	Consortium Partner	<i>The Municipality of De Figueira de Castelo Rodrigo (MFCR)</i>	Maria Inês Vicente
	Consortium Partner	<i>The Spanish Ministry of Economics, Industry and Competitiveness (MINECO)</i>	Borja Izquierdo

Internal Stakeholders	Linked Third Party	<i>Universität für Bodenkultur (BOKU)</i>	Daniel Dörler, Florian Heigel
	Linked Third Party	<i>Institut royal des Sciences naturelles de Belgique (IRSNB)</i>	Carole Paleco, Justine Jacquemin
	Linked Third Party	<i>University of Tartu</i>	Veljo Runnel, Sigrid Ots
	Linked Third Party	<i>Museum National D'Histoire Naturelle</i>	Romain Julliard, Anne Echassoux, Gregoire Lois
	Linked Third Party	<i>Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis</i>	Kostas Karatzas, Theodosios Kassandra
	Linked Third Party	<i>ESSRG</i>	Balint Balazs
	Linked Third Party	<i>Fondazione Grosseto Cultura (Museo di Storia Naturale della Maremma)</i>	Andrea Sforzi , Paola Talluri
	Linked Third Party	<i>Fundación IberCivis</i>	Francisco Sanz, Rosa Arias
Internal Stakeholders	EC Project Officer	<i>Horizon 2020 Research Framework Programme of the European Commission</i>	Colombe Warin
	EC Project Officer	<i>European Commission Directorate-General for Research & Innovation</i>	
Internal Stakeholders	Advisory Board	<i>Dr. Anne Bowser</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Baiba Pruse</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Prof Maria Attard</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Malgorzata Grodzinska-Jurczak</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Dr. Jaume Piera</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Dr. Henk Mulder</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Markus Weiskopf</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Dr. Prof. David Budtz Pedersen</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Rosy Mondardini</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Hester Volten</i>	
	Advisory Board	<i>Dr Kate Jones</i>	
Academia	Universities	<i>CS-related Research Groups: UCL ExCiteS, University of Leiden Citizen Science Lab</i>	Muki Haklay, Anne Land, Frans Snik,
	Universities	<i>CS Professors & Lecturers</i>	
	Universities	<i>CS Researchers, PostDocs & PhD Students</i>	
	Research Institutions	<i>CS-related Research Groups: ZSI, ILASA, JRC, NILU, Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research, German</i>	Sven Shade, Marisa Ponti, Aletta Bonn, Susanne Hecker

		<i>Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv)</i>	
	Research Institutions	<i>Principal Investigators, Researchers, PostDocs & PhD Students</i>	Barbara Kieslinger, Teresa Schäfer
	Museums	<i>Principal Investigators, Researchers, PostDocs & PhD Students</i>	Jessica Wardlaw, Lucy Robinson, John Tweddle, Julia Lorke, Andrea Sforzi, Katrin Vohland, Carole Paleco, Romain Julliard, Anne Echassoux, Gregoire Lois
	Science Shops	<i>Science Shop Coordinators, Researchers, PostDocs & PhD Students</i>	Dr. Emma McKenna
Educators	Primary Education	<i>Primary teachers</i>	
		<i>Club leaders and other extracurricular leaders (e.g. Science Clubs, Scouts)</i>	
		<i>Curriculum developers</i>	
		<i>Local Authorities</i>	
		<i>Parents Associations</i>	
		<i>Home School Networks</i>	
		<i>Teacher Associations</i>	
	Secondary Education	<i>Secondary teachers</i>	
		<i>Club leaders and other extracurricular leaders (e.g. Science Clubs, Scouts)</i>	
		<i>Curriculum developers</i>	
		<i>Local Authorities</i>	
		<i>Parents Associations</i>	
		<i>Home School Networks</i>	
		<i>Teacher Associations</i>	
	Museums	<i>Museum education and learning staff</i>	
		<i>Museum education programme coordinators</i>	
	NGO/CSO education and learning staff (e.g. National Parks)	<i>Informal learning leaders</i>	
		<i>Programme developers</i>	

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		<i>NGO/CSO education programme coordinators</i>	
The Public	Local communities		Local community residents
	Local community groups		Members of an interest group or community group
	Community centres		
	Special interest groups		
	Activist groups		
	Charities		
	Libraries		
	Youth Associations		
	Primary and Secondary school students		
	Hobbyists and amateur experts		
	Anyone interested in an issue, research question, or domain of research		
NGOs & CSOs	Citizen Science Associations & Networks	<i>ECSA, ACSA, CSA, The Asian CS Network, the African CS Association, the Global Citizen Science Partnership</i>	
	Museum Associations	<i>the Dutch Museums Association, The Science Museum Group, Commonwealth Association of Museums</i>	
	Science and Research Associations	<i>EUROPAC, IAPS, Association for Science Education, the British Ecological Society, the European Environmental Agency, ISPRA, EUSEA, ESOF</i>	
	Science Communications Associations	<i>ECSITE, the British Science Association</i>	
	Science Shops	<i>Network of Science Shops</i>	
	Global NGOs	<i>UNESCO,</i>	
	Science Media Centers	<i>EKLIPSE</i>	
	Other Associations	<i>Association of Universities, League of European Research,</i>	

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		<i>Open Knowledge Association</i>	
	FabLab Network		
	Maker Communities		
	European Schoolnet		
	Student Associations		
	Teacher Associations		
	European Children Universities		
	ICASE (International Council of Associations for Science Education)		

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APPENDIX 3 - Pre-Proposal Workshop in Berlin, 28 February 2018

During the proposal preparation phase, ECSA invited all who expressed interest in the topic of the H2020 Coordination and Support Action (CSA) Call to participate in a collective co-creative process to define the structure and content of the Platform, and the relevant stakeholders across the field of citizen science in Europe.

To this end, a workshop was held in Berlin on the 28th of February 2018, hosted by ECSA and the Museum für Naturkunde, with 24 attendees from 10 countries taking part. A full-group session was run to identify the relevant stakeholder groups, which was then broken out into three working groups to further discuss the framework needs, the community building & training needs, and the concept & methodology for the project, across each of the stakeholder groups (see Figure 9 below).

Figure 15: Images of some of the workshop session outcomes, 28 February 2018 in Berlin

The workshop constituted an important first step towards building up an understanding of the main groups of stakeholders within citizen science in general, and who the main users of the Platform might be.

Following a ‘descriptive’ stakeholder identification process as described in [Sections 2.1](#) and [2.2](#) above, the main actor groups within citizen science were identified as being:

1. The general public (including citizen scientists, NGOs and CSOs),
2. Academia (including career scientists),
3. Educators (including primary and secondary school teachers),
4. Policy makers and regulatory authorities in the field of environment, city planning, etc.,
5. Science journalists and science media, and
6. Industry and SMEs

This is the source of the main actor groups illustrated at the outset of this Report, in [Figure 4](#).

The groupings of core users of the EU-Citizen.Science platform that emerged from the brainstorm session have a slightly different profile, as shown in [Figure 10](#) below.

Figure 16: Initial stakeholder map for the EU-Citizen.Science Platform

In describing and assessing these Platform user groups, the workshop participants noted that they should include the following:

- Currently active actors in citizen science, as well as newcomers
- Decision makers and users of citizen science based data or solutions.
- Multiple types of users of citizen science guidelines, tools and materials - from those inexperienced, to citizens and scientists who already engage in citizen science activities
- Multiple users of best practice examples and relevant scientific outcomes, ranging from interested citizens through scientific institutions to politicians and the media.
- Members of the public - the citizen scientists themselves
- Those who are inexperienced in organising and supporting citizen science initiatives, and not necessarily trained in scientific practices.

These user groupings are developed and presented in more detail within Deliverable 2.2 ‘Multi-level platform Engagement & Community Building Plan’, and Deliverable 2.3 ‘Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report’. Here, they form a valuable input to the Stakeholder Register shared in [Section 6.7](#) below.

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APPENDIX 4 - COST Action WG2 Workshop in Brussels, 1-2 April 2019

The workshop entitled ‘*Building a community network for educators, teachers, Citizen Science practitioners and researchers on synergies between Citizen Science and Education*’ was organised and run by members of the Citizen Science COST Action CA15212 Working Group 2 ‘*Education*’, in collaboration with ECSA and other project partners. The main goal of the workshop was to effectively and sustainably connect the diverse stakeholders in the field of Citizen Science and Education by contributing to the development of:

- a) a platform that enables us to easily share existing resources and to collaborate openly on creating new ones, and
- b) a communication strategy that is tailored to the stakeholders’ needs.

“With a growing number of key players, the risks of duplications, competition and fragmentation increases. To avoid this, we decided to join forces and use this workshop to explore the needs of the community and develop a vision that would feed into the development of the new platform EU-Citizen.Science as well as a concrete communication strategy to collaborate and reach out to further stakeholders until the platform is established.”⁴⁵

Participants at the workshop came from nine different countries and represented teachers, educators, scientists, citizen science researchers, national hubs, the Citizen Science COST Action, the European Citizen Science Association, and EU-Citizen.Science.

In the first session, participants shared, clustered and discussed the ideas they had pre-prepared regarding what makes a lively community of practice in the field of citizen science and Education.

Figure 17: The CS COST Action WG2 Workshop

During the second session, participants looked at the profiles of potential platform users, in keeping with the [Personas and Pathways](#) approach taken from the Mozilla Open Leadership Training Series. The four key personas that the group chose to focus on were 1) Teachers, 2)

⁴⁵ Lorke, Julia. Thursday, June 27th, 2019. ‘*Workshop Report WG 2: Building a community network for educators, teachers, Citizen Science practitioners and researchers on synergies between Citizen Science and Education*’ <https://www.cs-eu.net/news/workshop-report-wg-2-building-community-network-educators-teachers-citizen-science>

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Science educators / Scientists, 3) CS participants, and 4) Informal educators. The group then discussed the characteristics of each identified persona, the expected pathway into the network, some of the key barriers to engagement, and possible solutions. These will form a key input to the Deliverable 2.3 *'Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report'*.

At the end of this second session, time was taken to identify actors who were not represented by the personas selected, and their relation to the proposed citizen science community network. These were, determined by category:

- Higher Education
 - Public engagement departments
 - University professionals
 - Degree programmes
 - Initial teacher education
- Teacher Leadership
 - Head of Department
 - Headteachers
 - Local Authority
- Other Education
 - Parent associations
 - Home school networks
 - Museum educators
- Programme/project managers within organisations
 - Government organisations (National Parks, Forestry etc)
 - Civic organisations (libraries, community hubs)
 - Non-profit/NGOs
- Media
 - Mainstream journalism
 - Social media influencers
- Policy Makers
 - Educational policy makers
 - Environmental/planning policy makers
- Trade Unions
- Wider community members
 - Retired/elderly people (often have time/money or come with young people)
 - Young people directly (not through formal/informal learning mechanisms)⁴⁶

⁴⁶ Lorke 2019

APPENDIX 5 - Joint Workshop with COST Action WG4 in Brussels, 10-11 April 2019

The workshop entitled ‘*Co-creating the European citizen science platform of the future*’ was organised by ECSA in co-operation with the Museum für Naturkunde (MfN) and the members of the Citizen Science COST Action CA15212 Working Group 4 ‘*Enhance the role of CS for civil society*’. It had the dual aim of actively contributing to the collaborative development of the Platform, and identifying potential collaborations between the ongoing COST Action and the Platform, throughout its development. The 18 participants from 11 countries in attendance were invited to share their expectations for the platform, and to contribute their expertise by identifying potential features and functionalities.

Following an exercise to allow participants to get to know each other, the opening session explained the EU-Citizen.Science platform to ensure that all participants had a good understanding of the platform and its aims. The next session was a collaborative exploration of the challenges of mainstreaming citizen science, such as:

- Raising awareness about CS
- Making CS part of more scientific activities
- Increasing participation among the public
- Ensuring scientists plan for citizens’ involvement as a central part of research

The participants discussed and debated these; there was broad agreement that it can and does mean all of these things. Following this, the participants were asked: what is the biggest challenge you face when mainstreaming citizen science? They wrote one sentence on a card in response and then ranked these through a game called ‘35’. During five rounds of scoring, participants paired up to assign seven points across the cards, sharing them according to the issue that was seen as most relevant. These scores were tallied to give each challenge a mark out of 35; these are shown in Table 6 below.

Table 6. Ranking of challenges to mainstreaming citizen science

Challenge	Score
Ignorance on policy level that leads to low awareness of the issue among people	22
Find places/opportunities to explain citizen science to “people not used to science” (minorities)	22
A lot of people are already doing citizen science, but they don’t call it ‘citizen science’, so it is hard to find them and connect with them	21
The biggest challenge is to find a (structured) way to include different citizen science initiatives so that many practitioners & newcomers in the field realize that they are to some extent part of the same group. The need to define citizen science can, therefore, come up.	21
Effort ≠ Outcome: comparing effort to outcome - one of the biggest challenges is to make the outcome more attractive - why should scientists make the effort to join citizens? (Researchers’ perspective)	20
Limited number of people (intermediaries / influencers) that can translate the need for citizen science to the general public	19
Increasing diversity of participants, reaching under-represented communities	19
Convince people that the task is useful and meaningful	19

(Local) governments, in general, don't know / understand what citizen science is and are not aware that citizens can contribute to tackling societal challenges	18
Raising awareness of the fact that citizen science can be a powerful tool to improve quality of life/ communities/ etc → concrete impacts, not just one more fun activity	18
To not disappoint participants on citizen science outputs and outcomes	17
Lack of funds	17
Convince citizens about the importance of science	16
Funding: the current funding system doesn't make it attractive for scientists to do citizen science	15
Time: people's lives are busy, there are already too many competing interests / activities / distractions	15
Engage all partners involved, all the way	13
Time-consuming (resource intensive!) e.g. local governments	13
Making people understand citizen science as different forms, structures and outcomes	10

In the second collaborative activity, participants were invited to think about possible users of the EU-Citizen.Science platform: their profile and their motivations for engaging with the platform. Each group of four created a profile for an imaginary platform user, as shown in Figure 12 below, defining who she/he is and listing motivations and barriers to using the future EU-Citizen.Science platform. Table 7 summarizes the profiles created.

Table 7. User profiles for EU-Citizen.Science

Who am I?	Reasons for me to engage with EU-Citizen.Science	Reasons for me not to engage with EU-Citizen.Science
<p>Dimitris Kostalas, a journalist “Tomorrow I need to have contents for my magazine. Oh look, a platform ...”</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Relevant articles for my country that I can embed into a national site -I can find good stories there (example: Nature Today, Netherlands) -I don't speak English but I can find something in my language, link to local activities -Free pictures, contents (acknowledge authors!), updates (subscribe to...) -I can connect to other journalists and understand how they deal with this citizen science -‘Hot topics’ -Links to other platforms -Collaborative approach with other projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Stories are not appealing / controversial / personal / enough -It's too difficult to find (Google can help us!) -Tagging is not good enough -It will be another boring EU project -I don't speak English ‘Old’ information
<p>Kristina, a biology teacher to 12-13 years old in Belgium “I found a way to make my pupils more active in my</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -To get tools, guidelines and materials (TGMs) and develop / innovate my project -To connect with other teachers and their citizen science initiatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Too much additional effort and time used for this -Doesn't know / ignores the existence of the EU-Citizen.Science platform -Not allowed by the school's director →

<p>class by installing nest boxes in the school's playground to observe the nesting process through a camera. I managed to engage other teachers in this project. The kids are very keen on participating in this and they are actively engaged in it.”</p>	<p>-Make the biology class more interesting for both teachers and pupils -To promote my project and its results -Add value to my own professional career -Increase the school's visibility</p>	<p>permission issue -Lack of support from the other teachers → afraid of involvement</p>
<p>A PhD student looking for arguments to convince her / his boss to do citizen science</p>	<p>-Not publishable -Data quality (improve) -Examples/success stories -Networking -Personal stories -Photos, not only text -Show ways how to engage public (H2020 calls)</p>	<p>-Language -Too focused on specific fields of science -Time engagement too big -How to find the platform? -Complex information / structure</p>
<p>A person working in the waste management industry: -burning some garbage -recycling some -complying to a lot of EU - regulations and standards</p> <p>Interested in citizen science because:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● We can focus on the CSB rules (public support, etc.) ● Open innovation (we love it!) ● To increase our transparency in front of the public ● Marketing ● Air quality for OVB neighbours ● Because OVB CEO wants it! 	<p>-To make similar projects (e.g. air quality sensors) -To look for inspiring examples of similar projects -To test new devices/solutions -To look for training materials on citizen science -To ask for help (Help. Help. Help. SOS!) -Tips for finding funds -Looking for partners (eg. research partners / building a consortium)</p>	<p>-Costly -Too complicated -Not in my language -Nobody will come anyway -I don't trust you -Low quality of inputs from the citizens -IPR issues -I can't find you online -You are not responding to my mail in three days</p>

Figure 12: Profile of an imaginary platform user

The second day started with a workshop where participants were asked to assess the state of citizen science in their own country or region, on a scale of 0 to 10. To unpack this further, they were also asked to explain specificities and think about the most important training needs to address. Table 8 lists the results of this exercise.

Table 8. Assessing the state of citizen science in participants' own countries

Country	Score	Specificities	Training needs
Albania	3	-Individual initiatives -Spontaneous/from researchers -Sporadic topics: Waste Air Quality -Media talk about it	-Creating an event specifically for Balkan countries
Lithuania	3-	-Not much in the media -Only international projects -Not one centre or rep. institution -No national strategy -Some scholars involved -In 2 / 3 years ... -Invisible citizen science projects	-Data quality & protocols (share what is already there) -Empowerment, inclusiveness and equity
Portugal	5	-In one year... -Moving up!	-Mentoring programme (better than training) better than

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -“Niches” -Scarce and sparse -Policymakers have been engaged (in the past) -Participatory budget -A website collecting citizen science projects -National meetings (2017/2019) -Two big projects (biodiversity) -Active labs -Not much in the news -Teachers not much aware -Strategy for citizenship 	<p>theoretical examples (continuous support)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Institutional incentives to use citizen science, how to do advocacy, not only to policymakers but also school boards, etc ... -Competition between countries or joint project
Czech Republic	5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -What does citizen science mean? -Crowdsourcing mapping -NGOs T-opics: Environment (water), nature -Popular in elementary schools -Policymakers absent 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Good / well-prepared examples but adapted to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -How to translate it to your local community? -How to [...] to offer local projects
Greece	3-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Air quality, birdwatching, wildlife, marine biology -‘Invisible’ citizen science (biodiversity) -Meteorology -Astronomy -No government funding -Researchers don’t know about it -More popular since 2015 	
Poland	4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Topics: Environmental, observations, Fab Labs -Only in big cities -No belonging to community/movement -‘Hobby’ -A few organizations for promoting it -‘Show us the money!’ -What is the advantage of it? -Barriers institutional / mental -Need for systemic change 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -No training; we need money
France	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -National recognition of citizen science -Ministry of Research / Education -To agronomy; big study in 2016 -National chapter for citizen science (Part. Science & Research) -Every research institute has it in their agenda -Infrastructure for citizen science is developing -Medical / cultural / eEnvironmental research - not connected -Mix (lots of things are citizen science) -Five years of research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Reuse as much as possible of what is already there and adapt to citizen science -How to change ways of doing things. -Relate to the stakeholders <ul style="list-style-type: none"> → I used to do that, but if I do that ... change research method -‘Everyone is doing it’
UK	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Five years old -Supported by big institutions -In public discourse: Public engagement (i.e. Science Festival involved) -Zooniverse -Strong push to open science -No clear rewarding system -Almost any researcher / cultural institutions would have done citizen science 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Product: How to communicate what you want to do -Service design process -How to use your (limited) resources efficiently (internal management, etc.) -Template for processes (especially for public institutions)

		-No national programmes	
Spain	9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Recognized discipline -National platform -Five national meetings -National Strategy for citizen science -Specific funding for citizen science (not mixed with public engagement) -Lots of initiatives (both bottom-up and institutional) -Lots of things in it (not citizen science) -Twitter chats with experts 	
Barcelona	10	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Seven years of citizen science: office of the city council (started as a group of five projects applying for funding to bring citizen science to schools and together) -Festival connecting municipalities, etc. → 15 projects -Big diversity of projects (biodiversity and social) -Co-creation with citizens in some projects -Connect with policymakers (city using the data) i.e. BioBlitzes -Criteria for assessing / letting projects in -Barrios adapted projects to co-create School, teacher trainings (use data to change things) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Good examples of good local projects - help us scale-up (to policymakers, etc) -If you don't have one, pick up one from another region/country -How to collaborate rather than compete (for funding) -Show how many people and who you need to set up a project citizen science
Flanders	8+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Citizen science definitely developing -List of criteria -Flemish government calls for citizen science projects -Stakeholder engagement encouraged in research calls -'Everybody SC' platform for citizen science + nature organizations (biodiversity) -20,000 → citizen science on the map <li style="padding-left: 20px;">In the media <li style="padding-left: 20px;">Made people aware (but not using citizen science name) -Cities getting interested -Bottom-up initiatives (e.g. air quality) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Networking - where/ how to find the right partners -Lots of scientists still think it's not applicable to their research
Netherlands	8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -95% of data provided (to EU) would not be known without citizen science -Everyone talking about it, but not as citizen science -Lots of initiatives -NWO: if you include citizen science in research you get A+ -Meetings etc. -On policy level → it is called citizen science! 	

The second day concluded with participants splitting into groups of four, where they drew the homepage of the EU-Citizen.Science platform, as they imagined it. During a plenary after these results were presented, the participants made additional comments:

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- Will it have consumer fragmentation or be product oriented? (Who am I or what I want to find here?)
- It could include a ‘What is citizen science?’ 3-minute movie
- It should highlight ‘star’ projects
- Don’t make it look like a project!
- It should have filters to sort information

As well as informing the Stakeholder Identification, these are all highly valuable inputs to the Deliverable 2.3 *‘Platform Functionality Requirements & Specifications Report’*.